

An Alternate Proposal for Peer Review

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Procedures for peer review of grant proposals and requests for telescope time have come under scrutiny because of demonstrated gender biases [1], [2], [3], [4], [5]. Studies of proposal success rates in the United States, Europe, and Canada involving major astronomical facilities both on the ground and in space reach similar conclusions: “proposals submitted by female PIs show a significantly lower probability of being allocated time”; “deficit in acceptance by female proposers is significant”; “proposals submitted by women were rated significantly worse than those submitted by men”; “significant gender-related systematic trend”; and “an overall signal favoring men.”

Recognizing this problem, the Space Telescope Science Institute (STScI) has experimented with new proposal formats. After trying two different stylistic changes,^a they experimented with a third variation, which required that proposals list investigators alphabetically without identifying the Principal Investigator (PI). STScI also examined their review process, which consists of an initial ranking of proposals made separately and individually by each reviewer, followed by an in-person meeting of the entire committee to continue the evaluation. Analysis of the first step, the independent individual ranking, revealed no

gender bias [6]. However, gender bias did arise in the second step, the group discussion. Professional observers of the committee deliberations noted that conversations focused on the PI, the team, and the laboratory about 50% of the time [7].

These results motivated STScI to devise a dual-anonymization procedure that completely eliminates the names (and institutions) of the Investigators from proposals in order to focus the review on the science [8], [9]. After proposals are selected, the names of investigators and their expertise and backgrounds can be revealed and reviewed by the committee. NASA’s Science Mission Directorate has initiated a dual-anonymous peer review procedure for several programs as well.^b These are admirable developments.

The creation of fully anonymous proposals represents a substantial change and introduces new constraints and added responsibilities for everyone involved in the peer review process. Dual-anonymization requires pre-screening of proposals by observatory staff to ensure stylistic compliance and creditable submission. Additionally, “levelers” are required in each meeting room to carefully follow reviewer discussions and interrupt when necessary to direct the topic back to the science. In addition, segments of the “old procedures” still exist as reviewers meet to discuss and evaluate proposals together.

A different, and in many ways superior, peer review procedure is suggested by a study sponsored by the National Academy of Sciences to assess the effectiveness of peer review. The study, by Cole and collaborators [10] of the National Science Foundation (NSF) peer review process, was carried out as part of a larger study by the National Academy of Sciences Committee on Science and Public Policy (COSPUP) [11].

Figure 1. The author in the Cassegrain cage of the 4m Mayall Telescope at Kitt Peak National Observatory.

Cole and collaborators studied three areas of research supported by NSF: chemical dynamics, economics, and solid-state physics. “Blue ribbon” NSF panels had previously ranked the proposals in each area. These proposals were in the traditional format in which the PI and team are identified. The same proposals were then given to a second set of equally “blue ribbon” panels for evaluation. The rankings of the proposals are shown in Figure 2, with the initial NSF rankings on the vertical axis and the new COSPUP rankings on the horizontal axis.

These results are illuminating. In all 3 subject areas, both panels easily identified and agreed on the best 3–4 proposals and the worst 3–4 proposals. However, proposals in the middle show little correlation between the scores. Cole and collaborators concluded that “getting a research grant depends to a significant extent on chance.”

The conclusions of this research lead us to suggest an alternate method of peer review and selection that has numerous advantages. Here, we outline this alternate method.

Without an in-person meeting, proposals (with proposers identified alphabetically) are read and ranked independently by the members of the review committee, and the scores are tabulated. The “top-ranked” proposals are accepted. The lowest-ranked proposals are rejected, similar to the triage process that occurs in the evaluation of HST proposals. The remaining proposals in the middle are selected randomly until the available observing time is filled.

This peer review method has many advantages:

- Follows procedures demonstrated to identify the best and worst proposals.

Figure 2. The NSF rank (y-axis) and the corresponding rank from the COSPUP reviewers (x-axis). The asterisks mark two proposals with identical ranks. I have inserted circles to mark extremes: the “best” and the “worst.” (From [10]. Reprinted with the permission of the American Association for the Advancement of Science.)

- Eliminates the step in which gender bias occurs, as documented by STSci studies: the face-to-face meeting of the panels.
- Allows out-of-the-box ideas to be selected.
- Eliminates gender bias.
- Potentially eliminates bias for race, career stage, institution, and nationality.
- Eliminates the need for detailed review (and disqualification) by observatory staff of a non-compliant proposal.
- Eliminates the need for staff levelers to oversee discussion sessions.
- Avoids committee preferences for small proposals that distribute resources to the many rather than restrict resources to a few.
- Saves money and time.
- Eliminates the challenge of writing “masked identity” proposals.

Some have argued that good science cannot be a random choice. This new process is not random. The best proposals will be successful. The worst proposals will not advance. The process explicitly acknowledges that the final selection under most current review systems is highly dependent on the peers who happen to be around the meeting table that day. Evidence-based research demonstrates that success with the current procedures already depends to a significant extent on chance. This may be an opportune time to initiate new procedures.

References

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Notes

^a In one proposal cycle, the PI and team were listed on the second page rather than the first. In another cycle, only the first initials of the PI and team were allowed.

^b <https://science.nasa.gov/researchers/dual-anonymous-peer-review>